

Ecology of Medicinal Plantago Species in Kohgiluyeh & Boyer-Ahmad Province, Iran

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Plantago, Climatic zoning, Medicinal plants, Rainfed cultivation, Kohgiluyeh & Boyer-Ahmad

ABSTRACT

Kohgiluyeh & Boyer-Ahmad Province has good potential for planting medicinal plants, given its climatic diversity and diverse plant cover, and therefore, locating medicinal plants based on climatic zoning is of particular importance. One of the plant species for cultivation in rainy conditions in the Kohgiluyeh & Boyer Ahmad province is the medicinal plant Plantaginaceae. In this study, the vegetation cover in this reserve was investigated and studied through field surveys during the growing seasons of 2023. *Plantago psyllium* L., *Plantago lanceolata* L., and *Plantago lagopus* L. can be placed in the one and two climate zones of this province. *Plantago major* L. is located in zone 1 of climatic zoning. *Plantago ovata* grows in Iran at altitudes above 2,500 meters in the Kohgiluyeh-Boyer Ahmad province. Also, *Plantago lanceolata* L. and *Plantago major* L. are located in one climate zone. Also, these plants (*Plantago ovata*, *Plantago lanceolata* L., and *Plantago major* L.) can be placed in the fourth zone (cold and semi-rainy). Therefore, on this basis, *Plantago ovata*, *Plantago psyllium*, *Plantago lanceolata*, and *Plantago lagopus* are suggested for rainfed cultivation in this province in four seasons.

Received: 8 February 2026; revised: 25 April 2026; accepted: 28 April 2026; and published online: 1 May 2026.

How to cite: Rahimi, A., Kamali, N., & Azimi Atergeleh, R. (2026). Ecology of *Plantago ovata*, *Plantago psyllium*, *Plantago lanceolata*, *Plantago lagopus*, and *Plantago major* L. medicinal plants in Kohgiluyeh & Boyer-Ahmad province, Iran, Sustainability and Biodiversity Conservation, 5(1): 1-17 DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19974426>

Introduction

Identifying native medicinal plants that have adapted to Iran's climatic conditions, to enable their cultivation and production on a large scale in the creation and exploitation of pastures, is one of the first steps for the mass production of these plants. Plant ecological studies include applied and fundamental research in the management of plant use (Fathi et al., 2014). The use of medicinal plants has led to an increase in the production of medicinal plants in developing countries. On the other hand, in recent decades, people around the world have been increasingly using medicines of natural origin, developing medicinal plants, processing and formulating new herbal medicines, and trading them globally, so that some Asians can benefit from the production of major herbal plants (Asadabadi, 2010). Due to its diverse climate and vegetation, Iran has good potential for entering the market of medicinal plants and herbs, which, in addition to treating diseases, can also create problems, self-sufficiency, and economic development in the country (Asadabadi, 2010). The Plantaginaceae family contains species that are of medical importance. One of the most important genera in this family is *Plantago* L. (Figure 1), which includes species whose therapeutic properties have been proven today, and at the top of them are the species *Plantago ovata* L., *Plantago psyllium* L., and *Plantago indica* L. (Odeh Mohammad-Ali et al., 2009).

Figure 1. Botanical characteristics of the three genera *Bougueria*, *Littorella*, and *Plantago* of the plantain family Plantaginaceae (Ghahraman, 2018)

The elevation difference of 500 to 4,000 meters between Kohgiluyeh & Boyer Ahmad province above sea level and the temperature difference of -10 to 45 °C demonstrate the wide range of tolerance of plant and animal species to survive in this region. In addition to providing

some of the wood needed by villagers and livestock feed, existing plant species are also important in terms of producing by-products, including gum, resin, flowers, fruits, nuts, seeds, roots, and leaves, often for medicinal and industrial uses (Environmental Protection of Kohgiluyeh & Boyer Ahmad, 2013). Plant ecological studies are among the applied and fundamental research in plant use management, and Kohgiluyeh & Boyer-Ahmad province, due to its climatic diversity and diverse plant cover, has good potential for planting medicinal plants. Accordingly, locating medicinal plants, including *Plantago*, based on climatic zoning, is of particular importance, and this study was conducted in this regard.

Materials and Methods

In this study, the vegetation cover in this reserve was investigated and studied through field surveys during the growing seasons of 2023. First, the plants were photographed and harvested. Then they were numbered and placed in a plastic bag and transferred to the laboratory of the Agricultural and Natural Resources Research Center of Kohgiluyeh and Boyer Ahmad Province as soon as possible. In order to be free from dust, dirt or mud on the roots, stems and leaves, the plants were washed with water, and then the dried or pest and diseased parts were separated with scissors, and water was extracted from the plants using blotting paper or clean newspaper. Then, in this study, the plants of the prepared samples were identified using the floras of Iranica (Rechinger, 1963-1998), and Iranian species (Masoumi, 1986, 1989, 1995, and 1998). Then, the native topography of this plant was investigated using knowledge of the medicinal plant Plantain and its ecology, the geographical, climatic, and weather conditions of Kohgiluyeh and Boyer-Ahmad province (A), and the different climatic zoning of Kohgiluyeh and Boyer-Ahmad province (B).

A: Geographical, climatic, and weather conditions of Kohgiluyeh and Boyer-Ahmad Province

Kohgiluyeh and Boyer-Ahmad Province, with an area of 16264 km², is located between 30 degrees and 9 minutes to 31 degrees and 32 minutes' north latitude and 49 degrees and 57 minutes to 50 degrees and 42 minutes' east longitude in southwestern Iran and is bordered by Chaharmahal and Bakhtiari Province to the north, Fars and Bushehr Provinces to the south, Isfahan and Fars Provinces to the east, and Khuzestan Province to the west (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Geographical location of Kohgiluyeh and Boyer-Ahmad Province

The peak of Mount Dena, with an altitude of 4,409 meters, is the highest point in the province, and its lowest point is Lishtar, with an altitude of 500 meters above sea level. Kohgiluyeh & Boyer-Ahmad Province is a relatively high mountainous land surrounded by the Zagros Mountains with parallel ranges to the north and east, and the Black and White Mountains, Khomi Khaiz, and Nile to the southeast. The Maroon, Bashar, Zohreh, Khersan, and Nazmakan rivers pass through this province and its highlands are the source of a number of rivers. 90% of the area of the region consists of highlands and hills. In cold regions, there are higher altitudes and more rolling hills, and in hot regions, there are lower altitudes and fewer rolling hills. Plains also make up about 20% of the province's area, and most agricultural land is usually located in the plains. Due to the geographical conditions of the province, the height of the mountains and the amount of rainfall and humidity decrease noticeably from the northeast to the southwest along the main stretch of the Zagros Mountains. This natural situation has created dual climatic characteristics and divided the province into two cold and tropical regions (Environmental Protection of Kohgiluyeh & Boyer-Ahmad, 2013):

a-Tropical region: This region is located in the south and west of the province, with an area of more than 8000 km², and has a hot and semi-arid climate. The rain begins in November and

continues intermittently until May. Compared to the cold region of Kohgiluyeh & Boyerahmad province, the rainfall is relatively low. Frosts also rarely occur in these areas. This part of Kohgiluyeh & Boyerahmad province has abundant mountain pistachio trees (Environmental Protection of Kohgiluyeh & Boyerahmad, 2013).

b- Cold zone: This zone, with an area of more than 6500 km² and an average altitude of about 2100 m above sea level, is located in the north and east of the province and adjacent to the provinces of Fars, Isfahan, and Chaharmahal and Bakhtiari. The average temperature of this zone varies from 36 °C in the hottest months of the year to -10 °C in the cold season (Environmental Protection of Kohgiluyeh & Boyerahmad, 2013).

Precipitation in this area usually begins in November and continues intermittently until May, and most of the precipitation is in the form of snow. This part of the province, which is actually the southernmost part of the humid Zagros, is covered with vast and beautiful oak forests and is the source of large, high-flowing rivers such as the Karun and Marun (Environmental Protection of Kohgiluyeh & Boyerahmad, 2013).

The frost season in the region begins in September in some parts and continues until late March. The absolute maximum relative humidity in April, December, and February is 100 percent, and the absolute minimum relative humidity in August and September is 57 percent and 63 percent. The maximum rainfall in April is 203.6 mm, and the minimum rainfall in August, September, and November is 0.3, 0.1, and 0.4 mm, respectively. The number of frost days in Yasouj city is 45 days, the highest number of which belongs to February and January (Environmental Protection of Kohgiluyeh & Boyerahmad, 2013).

In Kohgiluyeh & Boyerahmad province, winds blow from different directions, the most important of which are: **1- Monsoon winds:** These relatively strong winds are known as the north wind and the south wind. The north wind is a wind that penetrates the region from the northwest from the Mediterranean Sea and sometimes from the Atlantic Ocean. This wind blows in the direction of the passing of rain-producing clouds that enter the region from Lorestan Province and cause precipitation in the winter (Environmental Protection of Kohgiluyeh & Boyerahmad, 2013).

The south wind is another monsoon wind that penetrates the region from the south and southwest, especially in late spring and summer. This wind brings with it excessive heat and dryness and often causes extensive damage to the region's fields and agricultural products (Environmental Protection of Kohgiluyeh & Boyerahmad, 2013).

2- Local winds: In addition to the north and south monsoon winds that blow throughout the region, other winds also blow in various relatively limited and small areas of the province, which are known as local winds. The most important local winds are: 1. The chaos wind - blows at the head of the Upper Boyer Ahmad River, in such a way that it collects all the thorns, brushwood, and dry grass in the region and carries it away. This wind also blows in the tropical Lower Boyer Ahmad River, but it does not have a specific direction. 2. The wind under the sun - blows from the west in the Bahmei Ahmadi region at sunset, 3. The mountain wind blows from the northwest of the Bahmei Ahmadi region and is the tail of the same wind, 4. Surprised wind - Blows from the east in Boyer Ahmad Garmsir, 5. Bad Choghan - The strongest local wind in the region and usually blows in the Saqhawah of Lower Boyer Ahmad. This wind blows from the north in winter, and sometimes it may continue to blow with great intensity for up to seven days and nights (Environmental Protection of Kohgiluyeh & Boyerahmad, 2013).

The mountainous conditions of Kohgiluyeh & Boyerahmad province have led to a diverse ecological and biological diversity of plants and animals. The elevation difference of 500 to 4,000 m above sea level and the temperature difference of -10 to 45 °C demonstrate the wide range of tolerance of plant and animal species to survive in this region. In addition to providing some of the wood needed by villagers and livestock feed, existing plant species are also important in terms of producing by-products, including gum, resin, flowers, fruits, nuts, seeds, roots, and leaves, often for medicinal and industrial uses (Environmental Protection of Kohgiluyeh & Boyerahmad, 2013).

B: Climatic zoning of Kohgiluyeh & Boyerahmad Province

According to the climatic zoning using factor-cluster analysis (Clust Clustering with Ward's method ering with Ward's method), Kohgiluyeh & Boyerahmad province is divided into eight climatic zones: Zone 1 (cold mountainous with high precipitation): This zone, which includes the stations of Yasouj and Sisakht, has the highest precipitation among the eight existing zones. This zone, with 11% of the province's area, is about 2311 km². Zone 2 (warm and semi-arid): This

zone includes the stations of Dogonbadan, Basht, Ab Shirin, Dale, Cheram, and Lister, and has an average temperature of 21 °C and a rainfall of 437 mm per year. This zone covers about 3,121 km² of the province's area, with 23.1%. Zone 3 (Moderate Semi-Arid): This zone, which includes Margoon, covers an area of about 2271 km² of the province, with 14.5 percent. It has an average temperature of 13 °C degrees Celsius and 434 millimeters of rainfall. Zone 4 (cold and semi-rainy): This zone includes the northern areas of Dena County and Patavah Station, which covers about 2.7 percent, or approximately 1,121 km², of the province's area. It is the coldest region in these zones and has the lowest number of dusty days. It also has the highest rainfall in the province after zone one (cold, mountainous, and rainy). Zone 5 (very hot and humid, tropical): This zone, which includes the Babakalan and Bibi Hakimeh stations, has the highest average temperature, 24 °C. This zone has the smallest area, about 1000 km², at 6.4 percent. The average relative humidity in this zone is 48 percent, which is the highest humidity in the existing zones. Zone 6 (Central Semi-Arid and Semi-Temperate): This zone includes Quebecian, Lodab, Central Dehdasht, and Souq, which covers about 14.5% of the province's area. The average temperature in this region is 20 °C. The average rainfall in this region is 508 mm per year. Zone 7 (Hot and Dry): Representatives of this climatic zone include Liqak, Mombi, and Sar-Asyab Yousefi. This area covers 11 percent, or about 1,725 km², of the province's area and has the highest average number of dusty days and the lowest average rainfall among the existing areas. Zone 8 (Northern Semi-Hot and Semi-Arid): This climatic zone is represented by Dishmok, Qalea-e-Raisi, and Charrosa, which covers 8.5% of the province and has an area of 1325 km². The average temperature in this region is 21 °C, and the rainfall is 444 mm per year (Salehi et al., 2017).

Results

In Kohgiluyeh & Boyer-Ahmad Province, *Plantago psyllium* L. (Figure 3), *Plantago lanceolata* L. (Figure 4), and *Plantago lagopus* L. (Figure 5) were found in the mountainous region of Khamin. Mount Khamin is located 30 km northeast of Dogonbadan, the center of Gachsaran County in Kohgiluyeh & Boyer-Ahmad province. This area, which is located in the Zagros forests, has good vegetation. This mountainous region has a temperate semi-humid climate. *Plantago major* L. (Figure 6) was found natively in the Tang-Khushk region of Yasouj. The Tang-Khushk region is located in Boyer-Ahmad County in Kohgiluyeh & Boyer-Ahmad province, with an area of approximately 10,000 hectares and an altitude range between 2037 and

2600 meters above sea level, and is geographically located between 41°51' and 48°51' east longitude of the Greenwich meridian and 23°30' and 30°30' north latitude of the equator.

Plantago ovata (Figure 7) was found in Kohgiluyeh & Boyer-Ahmad province at altitudes above 2500 meters in Kohgiluyeh & Boyer-Ahmad provinces. Two important species of this genus, *Plantago psyllium* L. and *Plantago ovata* Forsk, have wide uses in industry and pharmacy in Iran. Also, bayonet plantain *Plantago lanceolata* L. and *Plantago major* L. were found in the Mukhtar district of Yasouj city, Boyer-Ahmad county in Kohgiluyeh & Boyer-Ahmad province.

Figure 3. *Plantago psyllium* L.

Figure 4. *Plantago lanceolata* L.

Figure 5. *Plantago lagopus* L.

Figure 6. *Plantago major* L.

Figure 7. *Plantago ovata* forsk

Discussion

Plantago psyllium L., *Plantago lanceolata* L., and *Plantago lagopus* L. were found in the mountainous region of Mount Khamin in Kohgiluyeh & Boyerahmad province, which with studies (Pai Pozan & Jafari Kokhdan, 2019) is consistent. *Plantago major* L. was found natively in the Tang-khushk region of Yasouj, and the Tang-Khushk region is located in Boyer-Ahmad County in Kohgiluyeh & Boyerahmad province, with an area of approximately 10,000 hectares and an altitude range between 2037 and 2600 meters above sea level, and is geographically located between 51°41' and 51°48' east longitude of the Greenwich meridian and 30°23' and 30°30' north latitude of the equator (Jafari Kokhdan & Bahrami, 2019). *Plantago psyllium* L., from the Plantaginaceae family, synonyms of *Plantago indica* L. and *Plantago arenaria* Waldst. & Kit. with English names *Fleawort*, *Clammy Plantain*, *Psyllium seed Fleawort*, and *Flaxseed plantain* (Mozaffarian, 1996). Annual plant, hairy, tuberous, short or relatively tall, height 30-150 cm, herbaceous stem, erect or creeping, simple or branched, leaves opposite, linear, narrow or lanceolate, flowers small, greenish white, spikes with many flowers, hairy tuberous, globose ovoid, with long peduncle. The time of its collection is August or late summer (Iranian Plant Network, 2024).

According to the climatic zoning using factor-cluster analysis, Kohgiluyeh & Boyerahmad province is divided into eight climatic zones. *Plantago psyllium* L., *Plantago lanceolata* L. and

Plantago lagopus L. can be placed in one climatic zoning zone (Salehi et al., 2017). Zone 1 (cold mountainous with high precipitation): This zone, which includes the stations of Yasouj and Sisakht, has the highest precipitation among the eight zones. This zone, with 11% of the province's area, is about 2311 km² (Salehi et al., 2017). Also, according to the results of a survey in Kohgiluyeh & Boyerahmad province, *Plantago psyllium* L., *Plantago lanceolata* L., and *Plantago lagopus* L. were found in the mountainous region of Mount Khamin, which is located 30 kilometers northeast of Dogonbadan, the center of Gachsaran County in Kohgiluyeh and Boyer-Ahmad Province (Pai Pozan & Jafari Kokhdan, 2019), which these plants can be placed in zone two, and zone two (warm and semi-arid): which includes the stations of Dogonbadan, Basht, Ab Shirin, Dayl, Cheram, and Lishtar, and has an average temperature of 21 degrees Celsius and a rainfall of 437 mm per year. This zone covers about 3121 km² of the province with 23.1% (Salehi et al., 2017). *Plantago lanceolata* L. and *Plantago major* L. were observed by the author in the Mokhtar region of Yasouj city, a part of Boyer-Ahmad County in Kohgiluyeh & Boyerahmad province, Salehi and colleagues (2017) state that these plants are located in a climatic zoning area using factor-cluster analysis.

Plantago lanceolata L. is a perennial herb, varying in height, growing to 30 and rarely to 68 cm. The plant has no stem and the leaves are all whorls. Glabrous or sparsely hairy. Has a short rhizome, unbranched or with very few branches, which leaves that are erect or ascending, with a relatively long petiole, almost as long as the leaf. Leaves narrow with a sharp tip or narrowly oval, narrowed on both sides of the broad, narrow at the base. The leaf margin is smooth or has small and scattered teeth, sometimes glabrous. The leaves are 10 to 25 or rarely up to 40 cm long and 1 to 3 and rarely up to 5 cm wide. They have 3 to 5 distinct veins. Peduncle erect, with scattered white hairs, up to 30 and rarely up to 60 cm long. Spike cylindrical or short conical, densely up to 3 and rarely up to 5.8 cm long. Leaf broadly ovate, more or less narrow, with irregular wavy margin, boat-shaped, 4 to 7 mm long. Sepals 2-2.4 mm long; Anterior sepals fused together, composed of two fused cusps, glabrous or with a few woolly hairs on the margin. Posterior sepals round-ovate, distinct, cuspidate, glabrous or with a few hairs on the upper margin. Petal lobes ovate or narrowly ovate, 2-2.5 mm long. Capsule ovoid, 2.2-4.5 mm long (Jani Ghorban, 2005), (Boissier, 1879) and (Patzak & Rechinger, 1965).

Plantago major L. was found natively in the Yasouj Tang-khushk zone located in Boyer-Ahmad County in Kohgiluyeh & Boyerahmad province, which is consistent with the results of (Pai Pozan & Jafari Kokhdan, 2019). The Yasouj Tangkhashk zone is located in Zone 1 of the climatic zoning using factor-cluster analysis (Salehi et al., 2017). *Plantago major* L. (Figure 5) is a perennial, rhizomatous perennial plant; the height of the plant varies and grows up to 31 centimeters and rarely up to 70 centimeters. It is stemless and has whorled leaves, so it does not die underfoot in park lawns and in pastures under the pressure of livestock and wildlife, and the terminal bud is not damaged. The plant is glabrous or has scattered hairs. The leaves are erect or ascending, with a relatively long petiole but shorter than the length of the leaf, broadly ovate-ovate to circular-ovate, with an almost smooth or almost convolute-toothed margin, glabrous or with scattered hairs. Leaves 5 to 31 cm long and 4 to 6, rarely 8 cm wide, with 3 to 7 distinct veins. Peduncle erect, up to 20 cm long, flowers in a spike inflorescence, a narrow cylinder up to 7, rarely 60 cm long. Lower and lateral leaflets similar, ovate-boat-shaped, 2 to 5 mm long. Sepals 1.5 to 2 mm long. Anterior sepals narrowly ovate; posterior sepals broad ovate. Petal lobes ovate, blunt-tipped, about 1 mm long. Ovoid capsule 2-2.5 mm long, containing 6 and rarely 30 small, angular seeds (Boissier, 1879) and (Patzak & Rechinger, 1965).

Plantago ovata forsk grows in Iran, including at altitudes above 2500 meters in Kohgiluyeh & Boyerahmad province (Naqdebadi et al, 1993). *Plantago ovata* forsk is an annual plant, stemless or with a very short stem covered with soft fibers, 7-30 cm tall, with long, narrow leaves, and spikes that are cylindrical or nearly circular or ovoid. The shoots usually grow from the lower part of the plant. This plant has a straight root 20-30 cm long, which is generally covered with numerous lateral roots. This plant belongs to the Plantaginaceae family. This plant has very small seeds, the weight of a thousand seeds is 1.1-1.9 g (Dari, 2016).

Plantago lagopus L. is a species of the genus *Plantago* (Mozaffarian, 1996). In addition to being used as a traditional medicine in many different countries, *Plantago lagopus* L. is also considered a refreshing food (Mozaffarian, 1992). *Plantago lagopus* L. was found in the mountainous region of Mount Khamin, which is located 30 km northeast of Dogonbadan, the center of Gachsaran County in Kohgiluyeh and Boyer-Ahmad Province. This area, which is located in the Zagros forests, has good vegetation cover. This mountainous region has a temperate semi-humid climate (Pai Pozan & Jafari Kokhdan, 2019).

Also, these plants (*Plantago ovata*, *Plantago lanceolata* L. and *Plantago major* L.) can be placed in zone four (cold and semi-rainy), which includes the northern areas of Dena County and Patavah Station, which covers about 2.7 percent, or approximately 1,121 Km², of the province's area, and is the coldest area in these zones and has the lowest number of dusty days. It also has the highest rainfall in the province after zone one (cold mountainous and heavy rainfall) (Salehi et al, 2017) and zone eight (semi-warm and semi-arid northern): includes Dishmok, Qale Raisi, and Charrosa, which covers 8.5% of the province's area and has an area of 1325 square kilometers. The average temperature in this zone is 21 degrees Celsius and the rainfall is 444 mm per year (Salehi et al, 2017).

Plantago psyllium L. and *Plantago ovata* Forsk. require a dry and cool climate during most of their growth period (Atal and Kapur, 1982). Also, climatic conditions in the final stage of growth greatly affect seed yield, and even mild rain is very harmful at this stage (National Industrial Information & Development Research Board, 2002). They are located in zones 1, 3, 6, and 8, with zone 6 (central semi-arid and semi-temperate) including Quebecian, Lodab, central Dehdasht, and Soug, which covers about 14.5 percent of the province's area. The average temperature in this area is 20°C. The average rainfall in this area is 508 mm per year (Salehi et al, 2017) and Zone Three (Moderate Semi-Arid): It includes Margoon with an area of about 2271 square kilometers and covers 14.5% of the province's area. It has an average temperature of 13°C and an annual rainfall of 434 mm (Salehi et al, 2017). Region 8 (Northern Semi-Hot and Semi-Arid): It includes Dishmok, Qala-e-Raisi, and Charrosa, covering 8.5% of the province and covering an area of 1325 km². The average temperature in this region is 21°C and the annual rainfall is 444 mm (Salehi et al, 2017). No plants of the *Plantago* genus have been reported in zones five and seven. According to the climatic zoning using factor-cluster analysis (Salehi et al, 2017), Kohgiluyeh & Boyer-Ahmad province, zone five (very hot and humid tropical), including Babakalan and Bibi-Hakimeh stations, has the highest average temperature, i.e. 24°C. This region has the smallest area of 6.4%, about 1000 square kilometers. The average relative humidity in this region is 48%, which is the highest humidity in the existing regions (Salehi et al, 2017) and the seventh region (hot and dry), includes Liqak, Mombi and Sar-Asyab Yousefi. This region covers 11% and about 1725 square kilometers of the province's area and has the highest average number of dusty days and the lowest average rainfall among the existing regions (Salehi et al, 2017).

During the growth period of *Plantago psyllium* L. and *Plantago ovata* Forsk, cool nights (low temperature) increase the growth and seed yield, and high night temperatures reduce the plant growth and number of flowers. In particular, sunny days and clear and warm weather are necessary during the ripening and harvesting periods (Atal & Kapur, 1982). Cool nights (low temperature), sunny days and clear and warm weather are located in zones 1, 2 and 4 of the climatic zoning using factor-cluster analysis (Salehi et al, 2017). Due to their fineness, *Plantago* seeds are mixed with sand or sifted animal manure (National Industrial Information & Development Research Board, 2002) and then sown at a depth of 0.5 cm (Atal & Kapur, 1982). However, dark plantain plants, due to their relative drought tolerance (Baghalian, 2010), require moderate irrigation (5 to 6 light irrigations) (Atal & Kapur, 1982) to complete their growth period and yield well. However, according to comments (Baghalian, 2010), this plant also tolerates high salinity.

The genus *Plantago* belongs to the Plantaginaceae family and has two important medicinal species, *Plantago ovata* forsk and *Plantago psyllium* L., which are known as psyllium in Iran. The husk powder of this plant is widely used in traditional medicine as a laxative. On the other hand, the husk of *Plantago ovata* forsk is considered a hydrocolloid fiber, and the beneficial effects of these fibers in the treatment of type 2 diabetes have been almost determined. Recent results from researchers studying this plant show that psyllium fiber has a significant effect on reducing cholesterol, fat, and blood sugar levels in diabetics, and also reduces the incidence of colon cancer. No specific side effects have been reported in patients treated with this fiber (Naqdibadi et al., 1993). The seeds of *Plantago ovata* forsk contain mucilage, protein, sugar, fixed oil and tannins. The resulting mucilage has two parts, one part is soluble in cold water and the other in hot water, the part soluble in hot water turns into a gel after cooling (McCredie and Whistler, 1965). Hydrolysis of these two parts yields D-xylose, L-arabinose and aldobiuronic acid. Its fixed oil consists of a glycoside called aucubine and various bases, several sugars, sterols and proteins (different parts of *Plantago ovata* forsk contain a glucoside called aucubine and a type of gummy carbohydrate called geselin and also has a high viscosity). The results showed that the leaf and seed extracts of *Plantago*, especially the leaf extract, are rich in phenolic compounds, flavonoids, and total anthocyanins. Based on the results, the highest amount of total phenols and flavonoids was found in the leaf extract. The highest amount of total anthocyanins was also reported in the leaf and seed extracts. The results of this study suggest that *Plantago* leaf

extract can be an accessible source of antioxidant compounds, especially total flavonoids, and given the role of antioxidants in preventing diseases caused by oxidants, it can be recommended as a medicinal plant for pharmacological studies (Zamani Chappardi et al., 2023). Also, after extraction, purification and optimization of the plantago seed gum, its moisture, ash, protein and carbohydrate contents were measured. Analysis of monosaccharides of Plantago seed gum by high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) showed that the dominant monosaccharides in this gum were arabinose and rhamnose (Niknam et al., 1998). The highest mucilage yield and maximum dry matter accumulation of *Plantago ovata* forsk were 17.39 g/m² and 497.56 g/m², respectively (Sepehri & Samadi, 2015). In traditional Iranian medicine books, numerous therapeutic effects have been mentioned for plants of the Plantago family, including relieving chest, throat, and tongue irritation, hot heart palpitations, relieving constipation caused by bile, heartburn, stomach and intestinal ulcers, joint pain, solid tumors, and hot inflammations, split ends, relieving heat-induced weight loss, and treating headaches associated with the stomach. *Plantago ovata* forsk has been introduced into modern medicine solely for the treatment of constipation, diarrhea, irritable bowel syndrome, and colon cancer, and more recently, diabetes and high blood cholesterol. The side effects mentioned for oral consumption of the whole seed powder of this plant in traditional medicine include severe sadness and grief, shortness of breath, inability to breathe, and sometimes death, which are compatible with the symptoms of anaphylactic shock mentioned in modern medicine. With these interpretations, there is a favorable basis for research on other therapeutic effects proposed for *Plantago ovata* forsk in traditional medicine texts and their confirmation or rejection based on new findings, and the mechanisms proposed for its side effects in these sources can also be considered and examined (Jafarpour et al., 2011).

Conclusion

Kohgiluyeh & Boyer Ahmad Province, with an area of 16246 Km² in southwestern Iran, an elevation difference of 500 to 4000 m above sea level, and a temperature difference of -10 to 45 degrees Celsius, geographical location, abundant plant diversity, and the growth ground for medicinal plants, is considered one of the most suitable regions of the country for the production of medicinal plants. Of the total 8,000 plant species in Iran, more than 2,000 species grow throughout this province. Of the total 1,200 medicinal plant species in the country, 475 species are found in the province, while the number of medicinal plant species in Europe is reported to be

800. Among the medicinal plants of the genus *Plantago* from the Plantaginaceae family in Kohgiluyeh & Boyer Ahmad province, *Plantago ovata* forsk at altitudes above 2500 meters (eastern and western Dana areas), *Plantago psyllium* L., *Plantago lanceolata* L. and *Plantago lagopus* L. in the mountainous region of Mount Khamin, the great plantain *Plantago major* in the Tang-Khushak region of Yasouj, Also, *Plantago lanceolata* L. and *Plantago major* L. were reported in the autonomous region of Yasouj city, a part of Boyer Ahmad county. The above plant species grow vegetatively and complete their life cycle with the atmospheric precipitation in the region. One of the aspects of this proper management is the study of wild plant species that are adapted to drought stress in dryland conditions and their cultivation. Among the plant species for cultivation in dryland conditions in Kohgiluyeh & Boyer-Ahmad province is the medicinal plant *Plantago*. *Plantago psyllium* L., *Plantago lanceolata* L., and *Plantago lagopus* L. can be found in zones one and two of the province's climate zoning. *Plantago major* L. is found in zone one of the climate zoning. *Plantago ovata* Forsk grows in Iran, including at altitudes above 2500 meters in Kohgiluyeh & Boyer-Ahmad province. Also, *Plantago lanceolata* L. and *Plantago major* L. are found in zone one of the climate zoning. Also, these plants (*Plantago ovata* forsk, *Plantago lanceolata* L., and *Plantago major* L.) can be found in zone four (cold and semi-arid).

Acknowledgements

Thanks to the Forests, Rangelands, and Watershed Research Department, Kohgiluyeh-Boyerahmad Agriculture and Natural Resources Research and Education Center, AREEO, Yasouj, Iran, for supporting the author.

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